

The Influence of Lifestyle and Product Diversity on Purchasing Decisions at BJO Sneakersmind Malang

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KEYWORDS: product diversification, consumer lifestyle, retail industry, purchase decisions, consumer behavior.

ABSTRACT: This research analyzes the determinants of consumer purchase decisions through an explanatory quantitative approach with a focus on lifestyle variables and product diversity at BJO Sneakersmind Malang. The research methodology used a sample of 100 consumer respondents with purposive sampling techniques and multiple linear regression analysis to evaluate the causal correlation between variables. Empirical findings show that consumer lifestyle has a significant positive influence on purchase intent with a t-value of 4.656 > t table of 1.661 and a significance of 0.000 < 0.05. Product diversity also demonstrated a substantial positive impact with t count 5,419 > t table 1,661 at identical significance levels. Simultaneous testing revealed that both independent variables simultaneously contributed significantly with F count 93.406 > F table 3.09. The adjusted R square determination coefficient of 0.651 indicates that 65.1% of the variation in purchasing decisions can be elaborated through lifestyle constructs and product diversification. The implications of this research provide theoretical contributions in the development of consumer behavior models as well as practical applications for the marketing strategy of the fashion retail industry.

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INTRODUCTION

The retail industry plays a fundamental role in the global economic ecosystem by providing goods and services to the end consumer through sales transactions in units or retail consumption individually without being resold. This retail business activity that emphasizes direct interaction between sellers and buyers has undergone a significant evolution by integrating physical store formats and e-commerce platforms to accommodate changing consumer preferences [1]. The transformation of Indonesia's retail industry that began in the 1980s shows a paradigm shift from the traditional retail system dominated by markets and small stalls to modern retail such as supermarkets, minimarkets, hypermarkets, and e-retailing which is increasingly appreciated by the wider community. These developments not only contribute to meeting the daily needs of consumers, but also have a significant impact on national economic growth and sustainable job creation.

Indonesia's strategic position in the global retail arena is reflected in the achievement of the fourth ranking in the Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) with a value of 53.0 and the national retail sales volume reached 407 billion US dollars or equivalent to Rp6,044 trillion, which shows an increase of one rank compared to 2019 despite facing pandemic challenges [2]. This achievement puts Indonesia below China with the highest GRDI reaching 4,072 billion US dollars, India in second place with a GRDI of 64.4, and Malaysia in third place with a GRDI of 54.1. An interesting phenomenon of Indonesian consumption patterns shows that clothing and fashion products rank at the top of the category of most frequently purchased goods, indicating a shift in consumption orientation from primary needs to durable products that have a long lifespan and do not wear out quickly [3]. The dominance of the fashion sector reflects the development of a culture of hedonism that prioritizes personal desires over basic needs, where branded and up-to-date products are an important parameter in the consumer purchase decision-making process.

Purchasing decisions as an integral component of consumer behavior include the complex process of how individuals choose, buy, and use goods or services that begin when consumers identify problems or needs triggered by internal or external stimuli to satisfy certain desires [4]. Rossanti's alternative perspective defines a purchase decision as the process of making a decision about a product

to be purchased after considering various brand alternatives and available information [5]. Indicators of purchasing decisions according to Kotler & Keller include product choice, brand choice, distribution channel choice, purchase quantity, and optimal purchase timing [4]. One of the determinants in the purchasing decision process is the consumer's lifestyle which reflects the individual's attitude in interpreting the actual problems contained in his or her mind as well as the tendency to integrate with various aspects related to psychological and emotional dimensions, including preferences and perspectives on certain objects [6].

Empirical research on the influence of lifestyle on purchase decisions showed mixed results, where Faulina & Susanti found that there was no significant influence of lifestyle on purchase decisions at Bhintang Ponsel Padang, while Silalahi & Hartati identified a positive influence of lifestyle on the purchase decision of Converse shoes in YKPN Yogyakarta students [7], [8]. In addition to lifestyle factors, product diversity is a vital strategy for companies to attract consumers' attention in making purchasing decisions by providing a variety of products that allow the fulfillment of heterogeneous consumer needs and preferences. According to the researcher, the concept of product diversity includes the entire product line and items offered by the company with four fundamental dimensions, namely width, length, depth, and consistency that help companies design effective marketing strategies to accommodate diverse consumer needs [9].

Product diversity indicators based on the results of the research include product brand variations, product completeness variations, product size variations, and product quality variations that contribute significantly to the consumer decision-making process [4]. Empirical validation from Siska & Safri shows that product diversity has a significant influence on purchasing decisions, in line with Simanjuntak's findings that identify the influence of product diversity on purchasing decisions in UD [10], [11]. Clinton Balige Shoe Shop. In the context of the fashion and sneaker industry in Malang City, BJO Sneakersmind as a retailer that has been operating since 2014 has built a reputation as a provider of high-quality shoes with trendy and innovative designs that are the main preference of shoe lovers due to the optimal combination of comfort, style, and material excellence.

BJO Sneakersmind, which is ranked second in the hierarchy of sneaker retail in Malang City, has competitive advantages in the form of a wide variety of products, competitive prices compared to official stores, strategic locations, and guarantees of product authenticity by presenting well-known brands such as Adidas, Converse, New Balance, Nike, Vans, and Puma in various product categories ranging from shoes, clothing, bags, hats, to fashion accessories. Analysis of BJO Sneakersmind sales data for the August 2024-January 2025 period shows significant fluctuations with a total of 4,010 transactions, of which there was an increase of 17.91% from August to September, a decrease of 12.42% in October, a further decrease of 8.9% in November, an increase of 17.22% in December, and a decrease of 10.17% in January 2025. An interesting phenomenon identified is that although BJO Sneakersmind has limitations in the diversity of products that suit the lifestyle of Malang consumers compared to its competitors, the sales volume still shows relatively high numbers every month, indicating the existence of specific factors that affect consumer loyalty and purchasing decisions at the location.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Lifestyle

Lifestyle is a representation of a person's lifestyle which is reflected in his activities, interests, and opinions in managing his time, finances, and preferences for certain products [4]. According to researchers, lifestyle also describes how individuals allocate resources to meet personal and social needs [12]. In the context of marketing, lifestyle is an important indicator because it affects consumption patterns and consumer decision-making processes towards a product. The lifestyle indicators used in this study consisted of activity, interest, and opinion, as expressed by Kotler and Keller and reinforced by Laksono & Iskandar [4], [6].

Product Diversity

Product diversity refers to the wide variety of products offered by a company to consumers. The researcher called diversity a strategy that allows producers to meet the needs of various market segments more optimally [4]. The diversity dimension includes brand variation, completeness, size, and product quality. This variety allows consumers to feel more satisfied because they have options that suit their personal preferences [13]. The higher the diversity of products offered, the greater the opportunity for consumers to make purchases loyally.

Purchase Decision

Purchase decisions are a series of processes that consumers experience in making choices for a product, starting from the identification of needs, search for information, evaluation of alternatives, to the final purchase decision [9]. This process is influenced not only by rational factors, but also by psychological and social factors. Indicators of purchasing decisions include aspects such as product choice, brand, distribution channel, time of purchase, and number of purchases [4]. The researcher added that previous experience and environmental conditions at the time of purchase also determine the intensity of consumers' purchasing decisions [12].

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is included in the explanatory research category with a quantitative approach. The main purpose of this type of research is to explain the causal relationship between the variables studied, namely lifestyle and product diversity on purchasing decisions. The quantitative approach is used because it is considered appropriate in measuring the amount of influence and significance of the relationship between variables through statistical calculations. The location of the study was determined at BJO Sneakersmind located in Malang City, East Java, with the scope of the research focusing on consumers who have purchased products at the store. The independent variables in this study consisted of lifestyle (X1) and product diversity (X2), while purchasing decisions acted as bound variables (Y). The population in this study is all consumers who have made purchases at BJO Sneakersmind during the period August 2024 to January 2025, with a total of 2,170 consumers. To determine the number of samples, the Slovin formula with a margin of error of 10% was used, which resulted in a sample of 100 respondents. The sampling technique used is non-probability sampling with a purposive sampling approach. The sample criteria include consumers between the ages of 20 and 45 years, have made at least one purchase, and made transactions in the period from January 2024 to June 2025.

The type of data used in this study consists of primary and secondary data. Primary data was obtained directly through a Google Form-based questionnaire which was shared with respondents through social media and directly at the store cashier location. The questionnaire is designed to measure consumers' perceptions of lifestyle, product diversity, and purchasing decisions. Meanwhile, secondary data was obtained from written sources such as reference books, scientific journals, previous research, and BJO Sneakersmind's internal documentation that is relevant to the research topic. The research instrument used was a questionnaire compiled based on the indicators of each variable. The measurement scale used in the questionnaire was a five-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" (score 1) to "strongly agree" (score 5). Lifestyle indicators refer to consumer activities, interests, and opinions as put forward by Schiffman and Wisenblit [12]. Meanwhile, product diversity indicators include brand variation, completeness, size, and product quality, according to Kotler and Keller's views [4]. The indicators for the purchase decision variables include product choice, brand choice, distribution channel, purchase time, and number of purchases.

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the measuring instrument, the validity and reliability of the questionnaire items were tested. The validity test is carried out by measuring the correlation between each item and the total score, and the item is said to be valid if the calculated r value is greater than or equal to the r -value of the table at a significance level of 5%. Meanwhile, the reliability test was carried out using Cronbach's Alpha method, with a threshold of 0.60. A higher alpha value indicates the consistency and stability of the instrument in measuring the variables under study. Data collection in this study was carried out through three main methods, namely questionnaires, observation, and documentation. Questionnaires are the main tool used to obtain direct responses from respondents regarding the variables studied. Observations were carried out at the research site to obtain a real picture of consumer purchasing behavior. Documentation is used to supplement data through historical records, such as number of buyer data, product catalogs, and internal store reports.

Data analysis was carried out in stages starting from descriptive analysis which aimed to describe the characteristics of respondents and the distribution of answers. Next, a classical assumption test was carried out to determine the feasibility of the regression model used. Normality tests were performed to ensure that the data distribution was close to normal, multicollinearity tests to identify correlations between independent variables, and heteroscedasticity tests to detect residual variance inequality between observations. If all assumptions are met, multiple linear regression analysis is used to test the influence of lifestyle variables and product diversity on purchasing decisions, either partially or simultaneously. The regression equation used is: $Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + e$, with Y as the purchase decision, X_1 as lifestyle, X_2 as product diversity, and e as an error. Next, a determination coefficient (R^2) analysis was carried out to measure how much variation in purchasing decisions can be explained by lifestyle and product diversity. A high R^2 value indicates that the model has strong predictive capabilities. Finally, the hypothesis test was carried out through the t -test (partial) and the F -test (simultaneous) to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variables on the bound variable at a significance level of 5%.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Respondent Characteristics

This study involved 100 respondents of BJO Sneakersmind Malang customers who were selected through the distribution of questionnaires using barcode media in stores. Based on gender, the majority of respondents were women (52%), compared to men (48%), reflecting the appeal of products that tend to be stronger in female consumers. In terms of age, consumers are dominated by the 20-24 year old group by 84%, indicating that the main market segmentation comes from young people and students. In terms of employment, as many as 64% of respondents are students who have earned an income, indicating that the main consumers are productive people who have independent purchasing power.

B. Instrument Test Results

The validity test is carried out to ensure that all statements are able to measure the construct of the research variables. The test results showed that all items in the variables Lifestyle (X1), Product Diversity (X2), and Purchase Decision (Y) had a value of

r calculated > r of the table and a significance value of < 0.05, which means it is valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test showed that the Cronbach Alpha value of all variables was above 0.60 (X1 = 0.745; X2 = 0.817; Y = 0.835), which indicates that the questionnaire is reliable enough to use.

Table 1 : Validity Test

Variable	Items	Calculation	Table	Sig.	Information
Lifestyle (x1)	X1.1.1	0,609	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.1.2	0,695	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.1.3	0,488	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.2.1	0,678	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.2.2	0,588	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.3.1	0,427	0,195	0	VALID
	X1.3.2	0,662	0,195	0	VALID
Product Diversity (X2)	X2.1.1	0,633	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.1.2	0,574	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.2.1	0,611	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.2.2	0,58	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.3.1	0,686	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.3.2	0,588	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.4.1	0,669	0,195	0	VALID
	X2.4.2	0,737	0,195	0	VALID
Purchase Decision (Y)	X2.4.3	0,681	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.1	0,535	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.2	0,592	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.3	0,588	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.4	0,501	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.5	0,685	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.6	0,537	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.7	0,523	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.8	0,63	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.9	0,643	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.10	0,613	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.11	0,53	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.12	0,705	0,195	0	VALID
	Y.1.1.13	0,474	0,195	0	VALID
Y.1.1.14	0,409	0,195	0	VALID	

Source: Data processed (2025)

Table 2: Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach Alpha	Standard	Information
Lifestyle (x1)	0,745	0,60	Reliable
Product Diversity (X2)	0,817	0,60	Reliable
Purchase Decision (Y)	0,835	0,60	Reliable

Source: Data processed (2025)

C. Descriptive Analysis

1. Lifestyle Variables (X1)

Lifestyle is measured through three indicators: activity, interests, and opinions. The highest average was found in the interest indicator (mean = 4.14), indicating that BJO consumers have a high interest in fashion and emerging footwear trends. The opinion indicator obtained an average of 4.00 and activity 3.96. This means that consumers' purchasing decisions are driven more by the desire to look stylish than functional needs. The overall average value of the variable is 4.01, which is quite high.

2. Product Diversity Variable (X2)

Four indicators of product diversity are analyzed: brand variety, completeness, size, and quality. The indicator with the highest mean is product quality (4.21), especially comfort (4.30). This confirms that BJO shoes are considered to be of good quality and in accordance with consumer expectations. The lowest average on the product completeness indicator (4.04) indicates that the type of product can still be developed more widely. The mean of the overall variable was 4.13.

3. Purchase Decision Variable (Y)

Purchasing decisions are analyzed from five indicators. The channel choice indicator (mean = 4.17) has the highest value, reflecting the importance of services, locations, and available stock. While the indicator with the lowest average is the time of purchase (3.83), indicating that purchases are more influenced by spontaneous needs than by routine frequency. The overall average value is 4.03, indicating that the purchase decision is in the high category.

D. Classical Assumption Test Results

The results of the normality test with the P-Plot graph show that the data is distributed normally, characterized by the spread of points following a diagonal line. The heteroscedasticity test showed the absence of a certain pattern in the distribution of points, so that the model was free of heteroscedasticity symptoms. In addition, the multicollinearity test showed a Tolerance value of 0.470 and VIF 2.218 for both independent variables, indicating that multicollinearity did not occur.

Figure 1. Normality Test

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Collinearity Statistic		Information
	Tolerance	VIVID	
Lifestyle (x1)	0,470	2,218	Multicollinearity does not occur
Product Diversity (X2)	0,470	2,218	Multicollinearity does not occur

Source: Data processed (2025)

E. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results

The multiple regression model shows that lifestyle and product diversity have a significant effect on purchasing decisions. The regression equation obtained is: $Y = 6.626 + 0.693X1 + 0.741X2$. The variable coefficient of product diversity is higher (0.741) than lifestyle (0.693), indicating that product diversity has a more dominant influence on purchasing decisions. This shows that the more varied and quality the products offered, the higher the tendency of consumers to make a purchase.

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis Results

Coefficient

Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIVID
1 (Constant)	6,626	3,675		1,803	0,074		
TOTALX1	0,693	0,149	0,403	4,656	0,000	0,470	2,128
TOTALX2	0,741	0,123	0,469	5,419	0,000	0,470	2,128

Source: Data processed (2025)

F. Coefficient of Determination

An adjusted R-square value of 0.651 indicates that 65.1% of the variation in purchasing decisions can be explained by lifestyle variables and product diversity, while the rest is influenced by other factors outside the model.

Table 5. Determination Analysis Results

Model Summaryb

Type	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.811a	0,658	0,651	3,91092

a. Predictors: (Constant), total_X2, total_X1

b. Dependent Variable: total_Y

Source: Data processed (2025)

G. Hypothesis Test

Partial tests showed that lifestyle and product diversity each had a significant influence on purchasing decisions, with a calculated t-value ($X1 = 4.656$; $X2 = 5.419$) is greater than t table (1.661), and the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$. Meanwhile, the simultaneous test resulted in an F count of $93.406 > F$ table 3.09 with a significance of 0.000, which means that lifestyle and product diversity together have a significant effect on purchasing decisions at BJO Sneakersmind.

Table 6. Partial Hypothesis Test Results

Variable	Stuttgart	Table	Sig.	Table Sig.	Information
Lifestyle (x1)	4,656	1,661	0,000	0,05	Significant
Product Diversity (X2)	5,419	1,661	0,000	0,05	Significant

Source: Data processed (2025)

Table 7. Simultaneous Hypothesis Test Results

Calculation	Ftable	Sig.	Table Sig.	Information
93,406	3,09	0,000	0,05	Significant

a. Predictors: (Constant), total_X2, total_X1

b. Dependent Variable: total_Y

Source: Data processed (2025)

DISCUSSION

Empirical analysis of 100 respondents using IBM SPSS Statistics 25 for Windows produced significant findings regarding the determinants of consumer purchase decisions at BJO Sneakersmind Malang. The findings of the study confirm that the lifestyle of consumers shows a positive and significant influence on purchase intention, as indicated by the calculated t value of 4.656 which exceeds the table t of 1.984 with a significance level of $0.000 < 0.05$. These results confirm the first hypothesis and are in line with the findings of Silalahi and Hartati, Permana, Akbar, and Rizma and Purwanto who identified lifestyle as a strong predictor in consumer decision-making, especially in the fashion product segment [8], [14], [15], [16]. However, these findings contrast with Faulina and Susanti's research which shows that there is no significant influence of lifestyle on purchasing decisions, possibly due to differences in product characteristics and market segmentation [7]. The descriptive evaluation revealed that the "Self" dimension (X1.6) obtained the highest mean of 4.43, followed by the "Fashion" dimension (X1.5) with a mean of 4.35, indicating a strong consumer orientation towards appearance and personal care aspects. In contrast, the "Environment" dimension (X1.8) shows a mean low of 3.69, indicating that environmental factors are not yet a dominant consideration in consumer purchasing decisions.

The product diversity variable demonstrated a positive and significant influence on the purchase decision with a calculated t value of 5.419 $>$ t table of 1.984 and a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, confirming the second hypothesis. These findings are consistent with the research of Siska and Safri, Simanjuntak, and Rizma and Purwanto which affirm the crucial role of product diversification in influencing consumer preferences [10], [11], [16]. Descriptive analysis showed that "Product Quality Variation" (X2.4) obtained the highest evaluation with a mean of 4.21, followed by "Product Size Variation" (X2.3) with a mean of 4.18, while "Product Brand Variation" (X2.1) showed the lowest mean of 3.87. Simultaneous testing using the F test resulted in an F value of 93.406 $>$ F table 3.09 with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$, confirming that lifestyle and product diversity simultaneously contribute significantly to purchasing decisions. These findings reinforce the results of Rizma and Purwanto's research which identified the simultaneous influence of the two variables on fashion product purchase decisions, indicating that consumers consider the suitability of products to personal lifestyle as well as the availability of product variations in the decision-making process [16].

CONCLUSION

The results of an empirical investigation of 100 respondents of BJO Sneakersmind customers confirmed the research hypothesis that lifestyle and product diversity simultaneously or partially exert a significant positive influence on consumer purchasing decisions. The lifestyle variable showed a regression coefficient of 0.693 with a t -value of 4.656 which exceeded the critical limit, indicating that consumer orientation towards activities, interests, and personal opinions is a determining factor in the decision-making process. Meanwhile, product diversity demonstrated a more dominant coefficient of 0.741 with a t count of 5.419, confirming that the diversification of brand variation, completeness, size, and product quality has a more substantial impact on consumer preferences. The determination coefficient of 65.1% showed the contribution of both variables in explaining the variance of purchase decisions, while the remaining 34.9% were influenced by external factors outside the research model.

The managerial implications of these findings indicate the need for an integrated marketing strategy that accommodates consumers' lifestyle aspirations while optimizing a diverse product portfolio. BJO Sneakersmind is advised to intensify lifestyle-based segmentation by strengthening its positioning as a retailer that understands the dynamics of contemporary fashion trends. Product diversification needs to be expanded through strategic collaborations with international brands and the development of private labels that reflect the unique identity of local consumers. The limitations of the study include a geographical scope limited to one retail location and a relatively short observation period. Future research is recommended to explore mediator variables such as price perception, service quality, and brand image, as well as apply longitudinal methodologies to analyze consumer behavior patterns in the long term.

Conflict of Interest

The researcher stated that there was no conflict of interest in the implementation of this research that could affect the objectivity and validity of the research findings. The entire research process was conducted independently without the intervention of third parties who have a financial or commercial interest in BJO Sneakersmind. The author affirms his commitment to academic integrity and transparency in the dissemination of research results for the benefit of scientific development.

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